

Olduvai Gorge – Chronostratigraphie, Climate, Ecosystem & Hominin Evolution

Structured Chronostratigraphic Reference Tool

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This is a summary of Olduvai Gorge research.

This document is a working chronostratigraphic synthesis compiled for personal research purposes. It integrates data from primary literature across stratigraphy, geochronology, palaeoclimatology, palaeoecology, and palaeoanthropology, with all entries referenced to their source publications. It is not a peer-reviewed work and should be treated accordingly: entries reflect the state of the literature as consulted during compilation and may not incorporate more recent findings. Errors and gaps are possible. The author welcomes corrections.

- **Olduvai Gorge** is a narrow valley, late Pleistocene through Holocene in age, incised into the southeastern margin of the Serengeti Plains of northern Tanzania, westward of major faults and volcanoes of the Eastern (Gregory) Rift Valley. It was an enclosed saline lake basin, **Olduvai Palaeolake** (n.a.: southeast-east from Olduvai Gorge there are the calderas of Lemagurut, Sadiman, Ngorongore and Olmoti volcanos).
- The Olduvai sedimentary basin was formed at ~2.0 Ma. When formed, the basin was an estimated 3500 km² in area and roughly circular, ~50 km wide and shallow (100 m) (Ashley and Hay, 2002) [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].
- The gorge contains two main branches, the Main Gorge and Side Gorge, which meet in the central 'Junction' area about 7 km from where the river discharges at Olbalbal [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010].

My Notes and My Question Marks (n.a.; ?)

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2015.10.005], [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact	
Namorod Ash											
Naisiusiu Beds											
Ndutu Beds		Age range between 60 and 32 ka , based on the available evidence [W.B. Reiner et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1002/ojpa.23292].		Upper Ndutu Beds	VCS,	Fauna reflects a dry, open paleoecological context [J.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].		(OGCP cores) A dominantly aeolian source, similar to that developed by hyperconcentrated flow reworking of aeolian sands described by Svendsen et al. (2003) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751]. VCS (Victoria Cabrera Site) The faunal assemblage includes <i>Alcelaphinae</i> , <i>Antilopinae</i> and <i>Equidae</i> [J.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].	OH 83, early Homo sapiens (partial calvarium), near archeological locality PLK and Loc. 23 (Hay, 1976), situated on the downthrown side of FLK Fault between the Fourth and 5th Faults on the north side of the main gorge [Whitney Brooke Reiner, 2017, (Dissertation), https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8sw0b1k], geologically dated to ca. 60 – 32 ka . OH 83 are at the fairly small and gracile range of modern human cranial variation [W.B. Reiner et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1002/ojpa.23292].	VCS (Victoria Cabrera Site, Infrared stimulated luminescence dating has provided ages between 90 and 70 ka BP for these layers that can be related to MIS 5a). MSA discoid and Levallois-based lithic assemblage. Lithic technology is based on the production of flakes obtained from prepared cores, with the discoid method and, to a lesser extent the Levallois method being the most frequently used. The retouched blanks are described as 'substratum' or 'domestic' tools (sidescrapers, notches or denticulates) [J.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].	
		~ 0.48 Ma [S. Hoare et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2020.105273].	AFT marker tuff [S. Hoare et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2020.105273].	Lower Ndutu Beds ?						The AFT marker tuff overlies the latest Acheulean , and underlies a series of early MSA occurrences [].	
		Ndutu basal contact at 0.50 ± 0.04 Ma (95% confidence interval) [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990].									
Masek Beds		700 ka (Hay 1976) [D.R. Sherrad et al., 2013, DOI: 10.3133/ofr20131306].	Norkillii Tuff (upper marker of Masek Beds)	Norkillii Mbr.							
		Masek basal contact at 0.82 ± 0.06 Ma (95% confidence interval) [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990].	Sub-Masek unconformity,								
Bed IV			Tuff IVB,								
Brunhes/Matuyama boundary at the middle of Bed IV would imply that this is at 773 ka (Singer, 2014) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773]. HEB assemblage was characterized as Acheulean : high proportion of bifaces (> 40%), well made handaxes and cleavers, many light-duty tools, bifacial points, and pitted anvils (Leakey and			... clay(ey) ...								
				Lake parasequence 11 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
				Paraconformity , pedogenic features, Borehole ZA							
				L1 (HEB, T4) claystone, sharp contact top	HEB T4,	Nearshore lake with drying out surfaces affected by pedogenesis and elsewhere ostracod-bearing . Transgression of Palaeolake Olduvai across the HEB site. Lake shallowing up [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].					(HEB, T4) Archaeologically sterile [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].
			L2 (HEB, T4),	L2a , clayey sandstone, sharp contact with L1 and diffuse contact with L2b	We suggest that the HEB stratigraphy is located above Tuff IVA , likely in the middle part of Bed IV , after depositional fill of an incised valley, and the lower parts of Bed IV are cut out by the incision surface [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	(HEB, T4) Sandy braided fluvial and overbank deposits. Lacustrine flooding surface [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				(HEB, T4) Archaeologically moderate (between 40 and 100 fossil and artifact specimens) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			L2b , silty sandstone		(HEB, T4) Sandy braided fluvial channel. Lake deepening up [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].					(HEB, T4) Archaeologically rare (less than 40 fossil and artifact specimens) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			Paraconformity , intraclasts								
			(HEB, T4) Thin claystone							(HEB, T4) Archaeologically dense (over 100 fossil and artifact	
				Lake parasequence 9 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	HEB T4,					(HEB, T4) Between level L2b and L3 , we uncovered a nearly complete postcranial skeleton of an Elephantid (rest on claystone above siltstone atop Level 3)	

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Roe, 1994). It has produced dozens of well made handaxes and cleavers, including one made from elephant bone , as well as thousands of faunal remains and numerous bone tools . T4 trench represents a relatively large Early Stone Age assemblage of cut-marked bones [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].								[J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].		specimens) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			L3 (HEB, T4), sandy siltstone overlain by a thin claystone. Nearshore lake with occasional drying out surfaces (shallowing upward)	Higher L3, Lower L3,	HEB T4,	(HEB, T4) Lower L3. Abandoned fluvial channel (low energy) filled by occasional flood events (deepening upward) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].					
			Paraconformity , pedogenic features								
			L4 (HEB, T4), sandy siltstone,	Lake parasequence 8 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	HEB T4,	(HEB, T4) Likely abandoned fluvial channel filled by flood events , with drying out surfaces [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				(HEB, T4) Archaeologically moderate [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			L4b (HEB, T4), clayey siltstone			(HEB, T4) Likely a backswamp or proximal lakeshore flats (shallowing upward) landscape [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				(HEB, T4) Archaeologically sterile [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			L5 (HEB, T4), claystone,		HEB T4,	(HEB, T4) Medial/distal lakeshore (includes lacustrine flooding surface). The claystone facies indicate a transgression of Palaeolake Olduvai across the HEB site [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				May be equivalent to the archaeological level 2a of Leakey and Roe (1994: 54) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
						Lacustrine flooding surface					
			L6 (HEB, T4), silty sandstone,		HEB T4,	(HEB, T4) Sandy fluvial bars or nearshore . The bones and artifacts were deposited in what appears to be a nearshore or floodplain context [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				(HEB, T4) Archaeologically dense [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	
			L7 (HEB, T4), bedded sandstone,		HEB T4,	Sandy fluvial (transverse?) bar deposits [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				(HEB, T4) Archaeologically very dense , (over 500 fossil and artifact specimens) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	(HEB, T4) Most of the fossils and artifacts derive from near the contact between L7 and L8. L7 correlates well to Leakey's archaeological level 3 and possibly her archaeological level 4. Numerous handaxes made from basalt, quartzite, and phonolite [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].
			Tuff IVA Clasts , conglomerate, sits unconformably on Bed III	L8 (HEB, T4),							Numerous handaxes made from basalt, quartzite, and phonolite [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].
				The disconformity below L8 has removed the lower half of Bed IV at HEB.							
			Tephrostratigraphic marker, Borehole Core 2A		Lake parasequence 7 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Borehole Core 2A [2°58'43.4"S, 35°19'25.5"E (1393 m)].	? ... Lake shallowing up (?) ... ? [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].				
			... clay(ey) ...								
			Paraconformity, Borehole Core 2A								
			... clay(ey) ...		Lake parasequence 6 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].						
		Tephrostratigraphic marker, ..., Borehole Core 2A			Borehole Core 2A	Lacustrine flooding surface (?) [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].					
		... clay(ey) ...									
		Paraconformity, Borehole Core 2A									
		... clay(ey) ...		Lake parasequence 5 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
		... stone									
		Disconformity, intraclasts, pedogenic features, Borehole Core 2A									
		... clay(ey) ...		Lake parasequence 4 [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
		... clay(ey) ...									
		Paraconformity, Borehole Core 2A									
		... clay(ey) ...		Lake parasequence 3							

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			... clay(ey) ...							
			Disconformity, pedogenic features, Borehole Core 2A							
			... clay(ey) ...							
			Tephrostratigraphic marker (Tuff IVA admixt ?), ...							
			... clay(ey) ...							
			Disconformity, gravel, conglomerate, Borehole Core 2A							
			... clay(ey) ...							
			gravel, conglomerate							
		Bed IV basal contact at 0.93 ± 0.08 Ma (95% confidence interval) [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990].	Disconformity, gravel, conglomerate & Paraconformity, Borehole Core 2A							
Bed III			Sandy claystone [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773]. JK2, Trench A: gray–brown silt, fine sand, coarser sand and silty clay on the bottom contact. In Trench B , the coarse sand thins into a medium-fine sand with minor basal disconformity with coarse sand and grit overlies gray silty clay. In Trench 8 , a coarse sand (upper archaeological layer at top and lower arch. Level at bottom) overlying a coarse sand/silty clay [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885].	Palaeolake Olduvai dominated	JK2,	Low-energy fluvial or locally deltaic environments at the JK2 site [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885].	Grazers that thrive in dry and open habitats dominate the JK2 assemblage : 80% Alcelaphini, 3% include Suidae, Rhinocerotidae, Hippopotamidae, Giraffidae, and Felidae; 2% include Hyaenidae and Elephantidae [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885].	Tooth and cut mark frequencies independently suggest that both hominins and carnivores had access to flesh, but neither indicate hominins or carnivores as the dominant consumers of flesh [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885]. Trench A artifacts: handaxes , fossil bones and teeth [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885].	The JK2 site preserves Tuff IID at its base marking the top of Bed II and it is capped by Bed IV allowing the site to be confidently confined within Bed II . The contact between Beds III and IV coincides approximately with the Matuyama–Brunhes boundary. On this basis, along with sedimentation rates, Hay (1994) roughly estimates the age of the top of Bed III to be 0.8 Ma. Therefore, the best estimate for the age of JK2 site is currently between 1.15 and 0.8 Ma [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885].	
			Sandy claystone [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
			Claystone [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
			Sandy claystone [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
			Clayey sandstone [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].							
			...							
									OH 82 was found on a scree slope eroding from the red claystones of Bed III , and could be traced to a fossiliferous horizon <2 m above the Bed II/III contact, near the Third Fault . It was a robust individual. We identify this specimen as a member of the human lineage separate from that of the other apes. We conclude that Bed III sediments date between 1.2 and 0.83 Ma, providing a median age of 1 Ma for OH 82 [L.J. Hlusko et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.22765].	
		Bed III basal contact at 1.14 ± 0.05 Ma (95% confidence interval) [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990]. Bed II / III transition dates to at least 1.15 Ma (Hay, 1976; McHenry et al., 2007) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].				Marks a change from a lake to a river-dominated system and a community shift reflecting greater aridity [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].				
Bed II,			Tuff IID overlying tuffs, have lower-Mg hornblende population and few sodic augites	Upper Bed II Mbr.	Sequence 5 ?					
Faulting during Bed II tilted the basin toward the east, and eventually the lake disappeared and fluvial incision was initiated [Alan L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].					Sequence 4 ?	LLK Loc 46, BK,				
Ecological continuity			Waxy clay (BK)				At BK, the largest meandering fluvial channel documented in Bed II [D. Uribealraa del Val & M. Dominguez-Rodrigo, 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.05.006]. The low-energy			
			Unit 4 (BK site) [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8].							
			Unit 3 (BK site) [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8].							
			Unit 2 (BK site) [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8].				The BK materials are preserved in low-energy fluvial deposits within a wide channel that has eroded the	At BK site , the remains of over 2 doz of Pelorovis oldowayensis , Syncerus , and Sivatherium individuals, in addition to thousands of stone tools was collected by the Leakeys in the 1950s. One of the	OH 9 (calvaria), LLK () , Loc 46 , Upper Bed II . The first appearance of H. erectus comes from sediments above Tuff IID [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2015.10.005].	Stratigraphically, BK site is situated directly above Tuff IID [J. Yravedra et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1111/bsr.12224]. Unit 2 and Unit 1 at BK site , the lowest units

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throughout the Bed II sequence. [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009]. Bed II interval corresponds to MIS Stages 40 to 64 [Jan G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.10.9656]. During Bed II deposition, the accretion rate was much slower (0.058 mm/yr) and cyclicity averaged 40.4 kyr, corresponding to Earth's orbital obliquity [Jan G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.10.9656].						river flowed from south to north [E. Organista et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.03.001]. Spot of dense vegetation along the watercourse, in a paleolandscape likely dominated by sparse/open vegetation [H. Arráz et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.05.010].	upper part of Bed II, including Tuff IID. The ancient river flowed from south to north and is currently only visible on the paleochannel's right margin [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8]. Level 5 (Unit 1) is the result of a flood event and the archaeological remains are interbedded on top of this silty-clay sediment [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8], in the channel's most active period [D. Uribelarrea del Val & M. Dominguez-Rodrigo, 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.05.006].	<i>Pelorovis</i> individuals was found in a vertical position, suggesting that this particular animal had died in a standing position after sinking in the mud. Other faunal remains: <i>Hystrix</i> sp., <i>Theropithecus</i> sp., <i>Crocodylus</i> sp., Antilopini, <i>Antidorcas recki</i> , Alcelaphini, <i>Metridiochoerus compactus</i> , <i>Equus oldowayensis</i> , <i>Giraffa</i> sp., <i>Hippopotamus</i> sp., <i>Elephas</i> sp. [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8].	OH 80 (nine hominin teeth, a distal humerus fragment, a proximal radius with much of its shaft, a femur shaft, and a tibia shaft fragment), Paranthropus boisei , Level 4 at BK (Bell's Korongo) site, Upper Bed II, 1.338 ± 0.024 Ma (1σ) [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2013, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080347].	contains the archaeological levels 1 and 2, & 3, 3b, 4, and 5 . Evidence of butchery [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8]. The raw material found at BK is quartzite and basalt. Hominins had a primary role in the accumulation, bulk defleshing and demarrowing of carcasses at BK4 (archaeological Unit 1 , geological Level 5 , in [E. Organista et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s12520-015-0241-8]) and post-depositionally ravaged by carnivores and rearrangement by sedimentary processes [E. Organista et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.03.001]. When analyzing cut marks, percussion marks, and tooth marks together, the results support early access by hominins to fleshed carcasses . Hominins at BK seem to have had access to large quantities of meat including, not insignificantly, from megafauna, and at BK level 4b surpasses the evidence documented from other early Pleistocene sites, including the more ancient FLK Zinj site (Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2010b) [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.015].
		1.3386 ± 0.024 Ma (1σ) [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2013, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080347].	Tuff IID, at DK site		DK,				OH 80 (nine hominin teeth, a distal humerus fragment, a proximal radius with much of its shaft, a femur shaft, a tibia shaft fragment), Paranthropus boisei , Level 4 at BK (Bell's Korongo) site, Upper Bed II, 1.338 ± 0.024 Ma (1σ) [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2013, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080347].	Large assemblage of Mode I stone tools , BK site, that are associated functionally with abundant vertebrate fossils (butchery damage occurs on fossils of ungulates of medium, large and very large body sizes) [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2013, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080347].
	Average accretion rate of ~0.058 mm/yr between Tuff IF and Tuff IID during 465 kyr, suggesting 40.4 kyr per cycle (about 2.4 m of sequence) [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.10.9656].	...			EF-HR,	The initial return of Palaeolake Olduvai to the EF-HR area, then the full return of the lake (diamictite facies) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005].				Correlations strongly suggest that the EF-HR archaeological site is situated between Tuffs IIC and IID , which would place it within the lower part of Leakey's (1971) Upper Bed II [L.J. McHenry & I.G. Stanistreet, 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.12.006] (n.a. hier?).
			Tuffaceous silty-clay with carbonate nodules, pale-yellow, SHKM (SHK main), [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004].		SHKM (SHK main),					
					SHKM (SHK main),		Avifaunal assemblage IIC (Upper Bed II: post Tuff IIC to Tuff IID) – EF-HR and FLK West Trench 69. EF-HR (Assemblage IIC) belongs in the lower part of Upper Bed II (<i>de la Torre et al., 2018 "a"; McHenry, 2018</i>). The LC and LSC correlate to the Lemuta Member and Lower Augitic Sandstone, respectively. The Acheulean locality of EF-HR is interpreted as a fluvially biased site. Cichlid fish are present at FLK West , but <i>Clarias</i> (catfish) are absent. From EF-HR, <i>Giraffa cf. stillei</i> (a small alcelaphine), <i>Megalotragus isaaci</i> , <i>Hippotragus gigas</i> , <i>Hippopotamus gorgops</i> , <i>Equus oldowayensis</i> were recovered, suggesting a more-open landscape , such as an ephemeral riverbank [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].			Archaeological Level C , SHKM , rests on top of the discontinuous clay layer , which is buried by the tuffaceous silty-clay [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004].
		~1.6 – 1.4 Ma . Our estimate for the undated Tuff IIC , which defines the top of Middle Bed II [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009].	Discontinuous clay layer top of Tuff IIC, showing an irregular and progressive contact with the tuff, SHKM [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004].		SHKM (SHK main),					
			Mudflat , SHKM (SHK main), dark olive brown, with abundant nodules of fossilized plant remains (seeds), periodically flooded [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004].							
		1.5 Ma [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2012, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0046414].	Facies contact between lacustrine and fluvialite sedimentation, containing archaeological Levels A and B , SHKM (SHK main). Clast-supported conglomerate, carbonate cemented [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004].		SHKM (SHK main), FC West , and East , MNK Main , MNK Trench 5 ,	At SHKM (SHK main), a fluvial channel and part of its adjacent overbank , both covered by the same tuff deposit (presumably corresponding to Tuff IIC) [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.004]. Paleoeological analysis at SHK (Sam Howard Korongo) Main Site reveal: Cluster 1 , wooded vegetation is prominent and large bodies of water or humidity exist, which in turn determines the high presence of bovini. Cluster 2 , a dominant woodland or bushland component, and a dry open landscape . Cluster 3 , mostly bushland or grassland with small portions of forest . Cluster 4 , composed of grassland-dominated or dry bushland parks , which possess the highest degree of vegetation openness and dryness [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.09.025]. Stream or river deposition recurred at FC West over time [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009].	SHK (Sam Howard Korongo) Main Site faunal assemblage: <i>Elephas</i> sp., <i>Hippopotamus</i> sp., <i>Sivatherium maurusium</i> , <i>Pelorovis</i> sp., <i>Megalotragus</i> sp., <i>Connochaetes</i> sp., <i>Alcelaphini</i> , <i>Redunca</i> sp., <i>Equus</i> sp., <i>Hipparion</i> sp., <i>Kolpochoerus</i> sp., <i>Crocodylus</i> sp., <i>Chelonia</i> , <i>Canis</i> sp. The processes contributing to the formation of the SHK faunal assemblage are natural death of megafauna, hominin processing of mega- and macrofauna (in the form of cut marks, percussion marks and impact flakes) and activity by carnivores [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.09.025].	OH 81 (parietal fragments), a ~2-year-old child, who suffered from a digestive physiology adapted to the regular consumption of meat (porotic hyperostosis induced by iron deficiency anemia), SHK (Sam Howard Korongo) site, 1.5 Ma old [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2012, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0046414].	Archaeo-unit B2 at SHK Extension , Developed Oldowan/Acheulean , resting on top of the bank, is deposited on the clays of the channel overbank and directly covered by the tuffaceous silt, is a very dense patch of remains, and coincides stratigraphically with Level B in SHKM. Archaeo-unit B1 "separation" is related to a variety of postdepositional processes operating in clay sediments [F. Diez-Martin et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1111/bor.12246]. Levels A and B (SHKM) coincide with those described by Leakey (1971) as 68b and 68c at the Main site. There have been archaeological gaps identified within the sedimentary sequence, indicating different depositional events within the sedimentary continuum, but taphonomic, metric and technical data confirm that, despite their different depositional context,	

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.10.005], [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact	
		Below the disconformity clay tuff FLKWa (FLKWa, 1.698 ± 0.015 Ma)	Clay tuff FLKWa								
			Tuff IIB,		MNK, MNK Skull, Loc. 88,	At the start of Middle Bed II, but during the development of the Tuff IIB, the lake made initial encroachments on the Junction Area [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005].				- <i>H. habilis</i> paratype (OH 13), OH 15 (cf. <i>H. erectus</i>) and an indeterminate hominin (OH 14) come from deposits associated with Tuff IIB at Loc 88 (MNK), while another hominin (OH 32) derives from higher sequences at the same site (Leakey et al., 1964; Leakey, 1971) [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010]. - OH 13, the last appearance (LAD) of <i>H. habilis</i> from Middle Bed II at Loc. 88 (MNK Skull) site [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010].	We take that the transition from Oldowan to Acheulean stone tool technologies at Olduvai occurs in the Middle Augitic Sandstone (around the level of Tuff IIB) [Stanistreet et al., submitted for publication; McHenry, submitted for publication], rather than just above Tuff IIA (Uribelarrea et al., in press) [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009].
		c. 1.7 Ma	Lower Augitic Sandstone (LAS) (also known as Leakey's (1971) Sandy Conglomerate (LSC)), is a traceable surface throughout the entire Olduvai Basin. - LAS is present at HWK-EE, HWK-E, HWK, HWK-W, FLK-S, FLK-W, FLK-N and FLK-NN [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.037].	According to Hay (1976), Uribelarrea et al. (2017) and this work, the LAS is present at HWK-EE, HWK-E, HWK, HWK-W, FLK-S, FLK-W, FLK-N and FLK-NN [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.037].		FLK sites (FLK, FLK N and FLK NN), HWK EE,	The 1.7 Myo LAS samples reveal a mosaic ecosystem, dominated by the presence of groundwater-fed rivers and aquatic plants and hydrothermal features. Between HWK-EE and FLK-W, the same river system formed the Lower Disconformity [A. Sistiaga et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1101/632414]. The general account at HWK EE, provided here suggests an open habitat with a permanent water source and trees, between Tuff IIA and IIB. Facies evidence suggests that the LAS was deposited by rivers under a more humid climatic setting, which were likely perennial or semi-perennial. The presence of both monocotyledonous (mostly Poaceae) and dicotyledonous plants. Elongate and spheroid (usually assigned to the Areaceae family) morphotypes with no decorated and decorated surface (echinate) were also abundant. Characteristic sedge plants phytoliths were also identified [I. de la Torre et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.07.018]. HWK and FLK sites are found in deposits of the same fluvial system, controlled by the same base level, and belong to the same landscape and paleosurface, but in environments with significant ecological differences. The only Acheulean industry accumulation is found at FLK-W, in a single downstream channel. FLK-W, the oldest (1.7 Ma) Acheulean site at Olduvai Gorge, is contemporary with HWK (HWK, HWK-E and HWK-EE Oldowan/ Developed Oldowan sites) [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.04.014].	Avifaunal assemblage IIA (pre-Tuff IIB) – HWK EE, MNK Skull, FLK West Trench 73. It spans the uppermost section of Lower Bed II and the lower portion (pre-Tuff IIB) of Middle Bed II. Pleistocene birds: Cormorants are the most common taxon present (27%), mostly <i>Phalacrocorax owrei</i> ; <i>Anhinga</i> ; <i>Pelecanus rufescens</i> appears to be restricted. Three accipitrids (<i>Accipiter tachiro</i> , <i>Accipiter cooperi</i> , <i>Aquila rapax</i>) occur at HWK EE. Aegyptiinae (vulture sub-family), is represented at HWK EE. Middle Bed II Passeriformes (perching birds) are limited to Assemblage IIA at HWK EE. HWK EE exhibits high diversity with an avian environmental signal, suggesting trees and flooded grasslands with a body of water deep and fresh enough to sustain a variety of fish. At the HWK Complex during lowermost Bed II (Prassack, 2014), a stronger tree and weaker emergent wetland signal are now evident. This environmental shift appears to begin in the upper portion of Lower Bed I (Leakey Clay), with the occurrence of vulture, raptor, and crow [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003]. The Bed II avifaunal community suggests a shift to a habitat mosaic of open waters lacking in emergent vegetation, and a more open mix of dry and wet grasslands and open woodlands through Middle and lowermost Upper Bed II from the wetland and lacustrine dominated system of lowermost Bed II (Prassack, 2014) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].	Bovid composition supports the presence of extensive grasslands during these times at HWK EE, while the fish data also support the presence of strong seasonality. The presence of fish, <i>Hippopotamus</i> and <i>Crocodylus</i> suggests abundant water at the site. Mammalian carnivores are rare overall, but more common in the LAS interval. Most are bone crunching specialists, such as canids and hyaenids [I. de la Torre et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.07.018]. Avifauna is abundant and diverse at HWK EE, and reflects a lake shore or wetland environment which, due to the presence of perching and tree-roosting taxa, attest to suitable roosting trees nearby [I. de la Torre et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.07.018].	At HWK EE site, OH (?) hominin fossil (root of a premolar), could not be identified to genus or species [I. de la Torre et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.07.018].	- HWK EE site records Oldowan technology in the Lower Augitic Sandstone at the base of Sequence 3, within Middle Bed II [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005]. - Quartzite dominates the (lithic) assemblage in terms of artefact frequency, chert and lava are the other relevant raw materials. The HWK EE lithic collection is characterised by cores and flakes, with variable frequencies of retouched tools and battered artefacts, attributed to the Oldowan sensu lato. Bone surface modifications indicative of carcass consumption are abundant in the HWK EE fossil assemblage, exhibiting both hominin and carnivore feeding traces indicating that they were occasionally feeding from and competing for the same carcasses at the site [I. de la Torre et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.07.018]. - At Maiko Gully, southeast from FLK-W, within the sandstones of LAS, faunal remains and Oldowan lithics can be found [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.04.014].
			At FLK sites (FLK, FLK N and FLK NN) (Leakey, 1971), LAS enclosed in the (green) waxy clay sediments [A. Sistiaga et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1101/632414].		FLK sites (FLK, FLK N and FLK NN),	The post-Lemuta transgressive sequence might date to 1.680 Ma [I.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001] (stratigraphic hier ?).					
			The boundary between Lower and Middle Bed II redefined at the disconformity between Sequences 2 and 3 (invalidated the use of Tuff IIA as boundary), that underlies the succession containing the Lower, Middle, and Upper Augitic Sandstones [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005]. The glacial most likely to have allowed the erosion of the major Type I incision surface preceding Lower Augitic Sandstone deposition would tentatively date to 1.65 Ma [I.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001].						Faunal turnover between Lower Bed II and Middle Bed II [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].		
			High-Ca plagioclase-bearing tuff (HCPT), a new composition that has so far not been identified in outcrop, above the level of the Tuff IIA [L.J. McHenry et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109630].								
			Lemuta Mbr. (comprises Hay's (1976) 'eolian tuff facies' in the Eastern Gorge)	Upper Lemuta	Lower Bed II Mbr.	Sequence 2					
		Revised dates give an age of 1.756 Ma for Curtis and Hay's (1972) K-Ar date, and 1.677 Ma (⁴⁰ Ar/ ³⁹ Ar isochron age) for Manega's (1993) date [L.J. McHenry & I.G. Stanistreet, 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.12.006].	Tuff IIA, is typically a tuffaceous sandstone. Tuff IIA is located within the middle of the Lemuta Member.	upper, dark, coarser unit			Tuff IIA (1.9 Ma) was deposited on a wet period and an expandet paleolake (cycle averages 21 ky) [G.M. Ashley, 2007, DOI: 10.1130/G24163A.1].				
			Lower Lemuta,								
		(n.a. 1.782 Ma ?)				A major change between lowermost Bed II and overlying Bed II lacustrine sediments includes an abrupt increase in quartz coupled with an increase in the zeolite analcime, consistent with the onset of more saline-alkaline conditions, contemporaneous with overall drier					

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.10.005], [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact
	1 cycle averages of 21 ky (?) [G.M. Ashley, 2007, DOI: 10.1130/G24163A.1].	...	At FKL N, clay	Lowermost Bed II? Lake Cycle 3, in Lowermost Bed II time, FKL N, lower lake level; spring water sourced from groundwater flowing from the Zinj Fault system [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	Sequence 1?	FKL N, <i>Deinotherium</i> Level,	The pluvial phase that filled the fluvial paleo-gorges that fed the earthy fill of Crocodile paleo-Valley would date to between 1.715 and 1.735 Ma [I.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001] FLK N, Level 1, and the <i>Deinotherium</i> find recorded by <i>Leakey (1971)</i> can now be shown to have a time separation of about one lake-parasequential period [I.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001]. Lake Cycles 4 , [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	(at FKL N) The animal (<i>Deinotherium</i>) probably died as a result of sinking into a swamp [Mary Douglas Leakey "Oiduvai Gorge", Volume 3. Excavations in Beds I and II, 1960-1963, 1971, ISBN: 9780521105187].		(at FKL N) Thirty-nine artefacts and manuports were found scattered among the bones of the <i>Deinotherium</i> , one chopper being actually within the pelvic girdle [Leakey, 1971]. Artifacts and faunal remains (archaeological site 40f of Leakey (1971)) occurs ~1.4 m above Tuff IF [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].
			Twiglet Tuff, exclusively in the 'Junction' area of the gorge.							
		...	Tuffaceous Clay, FLK N [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	Dry period (massive, freshwater carbonate deposit) between Lake Cycles 3 and 4 occurs at approximately the same level as site 40f [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].		HWK EE, VEK, MCK,	The presence of dicotyledonous woody vegetation and palm trees at HWK EE, VEK, and MCK sections above Tuff IF [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011]. The high diversity of anatids during lowermost Bed II was used by <i>Prassack (2014)</i> to infer an extensive network of small, eutrophic wetlands capable of sustaining a variety of water birds (sensu <i>Herremans, 1999</i>) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003]. Several freshwater sources are known from the HWK, HWKE, and VEK area at the same approximate level in Lowermost Bed II [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	A variety of water birds (sensu <i>Herremans, 1999</i>) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].		Significant stone artifact and vertebrate occurrences immediately prior to and after Tuff IF deposition [H. Stollhofen et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.09.024]. Scattered artifacts and faunal remains (site 40f of Leakey (1971)) , FLK N [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].
			- Bed I/Bed II boundary is the conformable top of Tuff IF. - BEDS I-II LOWER DISCONTINUITY , major extrapolation 1.774 Ma [Robert E. Jarrett, 2014, (Thesis), http://scholarworks.gsu.edu/geosciences_theses].				From the Tuff IF to Tuff IIA interval , a grassy woodland to wooded grassland mosaic existed at least from FLK through HWK-EE . Montane forest pollen frequencies were reduced in the upper portions of Bed I to an extent that suggests a drastic decrease in rainfall [Bonnefille, 1984]. Tuff IF records the maximal effects of drought . The top of Tuff IF , elsewhere in Bed I sections occurred <i>Typha</i> (fossil rhizomes of papyrus) marshes or reed marshes, and murid rodent taxa, the modern representatives of which live in marshes, on moist grasslands, and sedge belts that border lakes [Jaeger, 1976] [H. Stollhofen et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.09.024].			
	Average sediment accretion rate between CFCT and Tuff IF is 48.9 m in 212 kyr (or 0.23 mm/yr), period of the cycles is ~22.3 kyr (on average 5.1 m of each sequence) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].	1.803 ± 0.002 Ma Upper Section between Tuffs IB (~72.2 m depth) and IF (66.0 – 66.3 m depth)), sediment accumulation rate of 13 cm/kyr , and corresponds to a time span of ~40,500 years [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267].	Tuff IF source is the Olmoti Crater ~30 km away. The Naabi Ignimbrite in lower Bed I is compositionally similar to an ignimbrite exposed along the First Fault close to Ngorongoro Crater. None of the other lower Bed I tephra layers is correlative with the Ngorongoro Crater ignimbrite [L.J. McHenry et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2007.01.004].	Tuff IF Surge , geochemical type locality 40.	Tuff IF (1.9 Ma) was deposited on a dry lake bed (cycle averages 21 ky) [G.M. Ashley, 2007, DOI: 10.1130/G24163A.1], (n.a., FLK-N , a dry period – after Fig. 8) [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052]. The Upper Section should be visualized as the most distal toe end of the westward prograding fan-delta body [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267].		- During Tuff IF times, the saline-alkaline Lake Olduvai was not only fed by freshwater spring systems of lake-margin wetlands (<i>Deocampo and Ashley, 1999</i>) but also by shallow braided river channels associated with a volcanoclastic fan system draining the Volcanic Highlands at its eastern and southern margins. Beyond the former eastern lake margins there are evidence for the existence of temporary water sources such as floodplain pools, with a rich diversity of plants, including trees and palms. [H. Stollhofen et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.09.024].		An animal track way formed shallow depressions (lack of physical evidence of fluvial scour or a coarse sediment lag) on the surface, at FLK N , buried under reworked Tuff IF , as the lake rose during a renew wetter climate (Lake Cycle 3) [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	
		1.802 ± 0.002 Ma (n.a. NEW from Fig. 2 in [Stanistreet et al., 2020])		Tuff IF Lapilli , geochemical type locality 40.	The lake basin was almost empty when a terminal eruption from Olmoti Volcano laid down Tuff IF . Climatically, this time is marked by a coincidence of a minimum in the precessional variation at the top of Bed I and an obliquity minimum at the base of Bed II (hyper-arid phase) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].	HWK-East ,	At the time of Tuff IF is thought that the lake was virtually empty [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267]. - Saline-alkaline Paleolake Olduvai usually varied from about 8–15 km across but occasionally almost totally dried out , as at the time of Tuff IF emplacement [I.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001]. Adhesion ripples in the Tuff IF unit record prevailing northeasterly and easterly winds (<i>Hay, 1976; Stollhofen et al., 2008</i>) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].			
Bed I	The interval between deposition of Tuff IB and Tuff IF , and particularly just prior to Tuff IF , was characterized by repeated prolonged desiccation events and lake regression, up to complete drying of the lake [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109656].	The time period between Ng'aju Tuff and Tuff IF could be 22,000 yr [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	Paleosol with 4 Horizons, Bw, Bk, Bss1, and Bss2 (around sites FLK, FLK-N, and FLK-NN) [E.J. Beverly, G.M. Ashley, S.G. Driese, 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.10.005].	The ~1 km cross-section of this time-slice (around sites FLK, FLK-N, and FLK-NN) has a small topographic relief of ~1 m that affected thickness, number, and vertic development of paleosols on the landscape, with faults, freshwater springs (i.e. tufa) fault-controlled and vegetation [E.J. Beverly, G.M. Ashley, S.G. Driese, 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	Levels 1 & 2, FLK-N , formed under increasingly arid conditions [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	Upper Bed I Mbr. Sedimentation rate for upper Bed I (~0.1 mm/yr) [G.M. Ashley, 2007, DOI: 10.1130/G24163A.1]. The last ~20 ka of uppermost Bed I are increasingly arid due to the decrease in rainfall associated with the dry phase of the precession cycle [E.J. Beverly, G.M. Ashley, S.G. Driese, 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	HWK-East , around the sites FLK, FLK-N, and FLK-NN ,	Herbaceous ground cover colonised a fluvio-deltaic floodplain developed on a dried out lake bed, following pronounced lake retreat of saline-alkaline palaeo-Lake Olduvai during a developing dry climatic phase and covered by the initial pyroclastic ash surge unit of Tuff IF (Trench 113, HWK-East). The term 'grassland' as used here implies low vegetation cover including mostly grasses and some sedges and forbs. During successive minor lake withdrawals the grasses became established on the flat-gradient, well-drained mudflats. During minor lake transgression the grassland was then covered by brown waxy clay. This succession repeated at least three times before erosion and deposition of the subaerial IF ashes [M.K. Bamford et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.09.003]. The last ~20 ka of uppermost Bed I (around sites FLK, FLK-N, and FLK-NN) are increasingly arid due to the decrease in rainfall associated with the dry phase of the precession cycle [E.J. Beverly, G.M. Ashley, S.G. Driese, 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.10.005].	The marked abundance of <i>Antidorcas recki</i> and <i>Parmularius altidens</i> , Antilopini, Hippotragini (horse antelopes) a variety of carnivores (<i>Panthera pardus</i> , aff. <i>Panthera leo</i> , <i>Crocuta crocuta</i> , <i>Dinofelis</i> sp., <i>Canis</i> sp.), a larger buffalo, <i>Syncerus acoelotus</i> , Suids (<i>Kolpochocerus limnetes</i> , <i>Metridiochocerus andrewsi</i>), <i>Equus oldowayensis</i> , <i>Hipparion</i> sp., <i>Hippopotamus gorgops</i> , <i>Ceratotherium simum</i> , a giraffid, <i>Sivatherium maurusium</i> , <i>Theropithecus</i> , at FLK North levels 1–2 , exhibits a continuing high incidence of trampling and sedimentary abrasion marks [H.T. Brunn et al., 2010, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2010.06.004].	Significant stone artifact and vertebrate occurrences immediately prior to and after Tuff IF deposition [H. Stollhofen et al., 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2007.09.024]. Hominin subsistence activities at FLK North levels 1–2 , were ephemeral and minor at a location dominated by felid behavior , a short-term stop for foraging hominins rather than a more leisurely living floor or home base. The stone tools were predominantly related to battering activities , and have been focused on the processing of plant resources [H.T. Brunn et al., 2010, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2010.06.004].
				Level 3, FLK-N , was formed as drying continued [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].					Level 3, FLK-N , bone assemblages are dominated by two taxa: <i>P. altidens</i> and <i>A. recki</i> which indicates specialized carcass collectors, such as felids [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].	
				Level 4, FLK-N , formed as the climate became drier [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].						Level 4, FLK-N , has a robust carnivore signal [G.M. Ashley et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.052].

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.10.005], [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact	
					57,	hominid locality was a stream in a small valley incised into the western lake margin during a period of low lake level. Ephemeral fluvial flooding conditions. Well oxygenated (flowing, shallow) water (a stream) [R.J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.1075374]. The change toward drier, more open habitats took place in Bed I between 1.85 and 1.80 Ma (Tuffs IB–ID), prior to the local transition from Oldowan to Acheulean technologies within Middle Bed II at ~1.66 Ma [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009]. Weaker freshening event (event 5) in the paleo-Lake Olduvai basin occurred ca. 1.84 Ma [D.M. Deocampo et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1130/G38950.1].		Hippopotamus, and fish. The presence of <i>Antidorcas</i> , <i>Beatragus</i> or <i>Connachaetes</i> , <i>Gazella</i> or <i>Aepyceros</i> , <i>Kobus</i> , <i>Megalotragus</i> , and <i>Parmularius</i> grazed plants with C ₄ photosynthetic pathway. The presence of <i>Papio</i> and modern landscape analogs suggest that the stream may have supported a gallery woodland [R.J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.1075374].	and lower face), Homo habilis holotype, from the western portion of the Bed I , (Loc. 64/Trench 57), Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania , maximum age of 1.839 ± 0.005 Ma [R. J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.1075374]. OH 65 must be older than 1.79 Ma (Hay & Kyser, 2001) and younger than 1.839 ± 0.005 Ma (age of Tuff IC; Blumenschine et al., 2003) [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010]. Loc 64 'hominin channel-fill sandstone' assigned to Tuff ID by McHenry (2012) is ambiguous. The 'channel-fill sandstone' is dominated by Tuff ID material. The volcanoclastic sandstones, tentatively identified as Tuff ID sit on a regional incision surface (fluvially channelized incision) (Blumenschine et al., 2003)), involving both disconformity and paraconformity developments [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026].	vertebrate fossils , Loc. 64/Trench 57, some of which show evidence of butchery . Stone knife cut marks and hammerstone percussion marks are evident on mammal bone are three to five times lower than that expected if hominids extracted all available flesh and marrow, contrasting with the occurrences of butchery marking in the FLK 22 (<i>Zinjanthropus</i> level) assemblage from the eastern Bed I lake margin. The stone artifacts include a range of typically Oldowan core forms, 92% of which are made on quartzite like that found on outcrops near the western gorge, and some made of lavas [R. J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.1075374].	
		1.848 Ma interpolated age. (1.839 ± 0.005 Ma) [R. J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.1075374]. (Use 1.843 Ma , better timeline fit than Deino date [Robert E. Jarrett, 2014, (Thesis), http://scholarworks.asu.edu/geosciences_theses])	Tuff IC , geochemical type locality 45b, 64 (glass) (feldspar, augite, and titanomagnetite composition). Tuff IC , previously identified only in the Junction, is now identified geochemically to the west of the lake deposits, where it is much finer and fresher. 1.843 Ma , better timeline fit than Deino date [Robert E. Jarrett, 2014, (Thesis), http://scholarworks.asu.edu/geosciences_theses])	(FLK (Hay, 1976: Locality 45)) Crystal-poor fine ash tuff, 7–12 cm thick with a rooted top. (FLK (Hay, 1976: Locality 45)) Pumice-lapilli-bearing, feldspar and augite crystal-rich base; contains imprints of in situ subaerial parts of subvertical sedges that are bent/inclined westward, suggesting tractional currents during Tuff IC emplacement (westwardly travelling very dilute surges). Elsewhere the ash fallout mantled existing vegetation and favored its in situ pristine preservation.	FLK (Hay, 1976: Locality 45)	Tuff IC preserves the paleosurface of the landscape intact [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023]. Evidence of freshwater and preserved marshland vegetation buried by Tuff IC, at KK W just east of FLK (Bamford, 2012) [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267].				Tuff IC is in direct contact with the archaeological remains of the upper Zinj level [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	
			(At FLK sites: FLK, FLK N and FLK NN) (Leakey, 1971), Green waxy clay sediments overlain by Tuff IC [A. Sistiaga et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1101/632414]. Zinj clay , was deposited over CHT in the whole study area except within the highest energy area, and consists of two continuous transgressive events with clay deposition , each containing separate archaeological levels. Here, we will refer to the paleosurface underlying Tuff IC as the Zinj paleosurface or Zinj paleolandscape . An ubiquitous horizon throughout the studied area is what we call ' Zinj clay ', which is equivalent to layer 22 from the FLK Zinj sequence as described by Leakey (1971) [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023]. Zinj clay contains the pene-contemporaneous FLK Zinj-DS-PTK-AMK complex [D.M. Martin-Perea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.018]. Level 22 (Zinj clay) overlies the Chapatti Tuff (CHT) and it is overlain by Tuff IC. It can be suggested that during the deposition of levels 22A and 22B there was a differential entry of fresh water into the basin throughout the palaeolandscape. Sedimentary conditions must have occurred in very low energy conditions throughout the clay sequence of this stratum [D.M. Martin-Perea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.018].	The upper Zinj clay unit is more earthy. Level 22A, FLK Zinj-DS-PTK-AMK complex , dark olive grey earthy clay. A more hydrologically closed system for level 22A , with higher salinity and alkalinity than level 22B [D.M. Martin-Perea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.018]. Silt (only at DS site) [D.M. Martin-Perea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.018]. The lower unit is more waxy and always contains more clay. Level 22B, FLK Zinj-DS-PTK-AMK complex , waxier, darker clay [D.M. Martin-Perea et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.09.018].	Three lake-parasequential periods, each with 4200 years average, between Tuff IB (1.845 ± 0.002 Ma) and Tuff IC (1.839 ± 0.005 Ma) [J.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001]. Lake-parasequences 1 (1.849.200 – 1.845 Ma) (Zinj clay, Zinj site) (n.a. after Fig. 5 [J.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001]). The <i>Zinjanthropus</i> land surface is an erosional surface incised after a withdrawal of the paleolake to the west and associated base-level fall [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006].	PKT (Level 1), FLK Complex (FLK Zinj Level 22, FLK N, FLK NN, FLK S), FLK NN Level 1, DDH ,	The landscape facets include a 0.5–1.0 m high, lightly wooded Peninsula in the area of FLK, with a very low-gradient River Channel or Spillway to the south (FLK S) and a freshwater Wetland (FLK N and FLK NN) , directed towards the lake shoreline to the north. The Wetland is divided into two sub-facets, an expansive Wetland Interior (FLK NN) , located along the eastern lake margin, and the Wetland Edge (FLK N) , a narrow zone occurring at the ecotone of the Wetland and Peninsula (mosaic of marshland, woodland, bushland and grass/sedgeland environments) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2010, DOI: 10.3853/j.0067-1975.62.2010.1541]. A low energy environment corresponding to lake-margin sedimentation during a high stand of the lake . FLK Zinj has two paleolandscape division: the topographically higher supralittoral, where a palm and Acacia woodland developed (FLK-Zinj proper), and the topographically lower littoral with a freshwater spring surrounded by a wetland (FLK-NN) . FLK Zinj-PTK strip with no evidence of large rivers crossing it [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023]. Assemblage IB , the interval from which the OH 5 Zinjanthropus cranium derives, shows a dominance of wetland habitats , supporting previous data for wetter conditions at this time. Ecological continuity throughout the Bed II sequence [F. Bibi et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.10.009].	The holotype of Crocodylus anthropophagus (new horned crocodile species) , NNHM-OLD-1001 (partial skull and skeleton), was collected from the surface of Middle Bed I, between Tuffs IB and IC , as surface find. An anteroposterior crest that takes the form of a long continuous ridge is the cranial ornamentation features that diagnose <i>C. anthropophagus</i> and distinguish it from most other Neogene crocodylines [C. A. Brochu et al., 2010, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0009333]. Shorebirds dominate the avifauna at the hominid bearing deposits in the FLK Complex : Charadriiformes, a variety of lake and wetland taxa , including grebes, rails, ducks and birds typical of bush, grass, and open woodland, aerial predators : => (for Wetland Interior, FLK NN Perennial wetlands (marsh), emergent vegetation, standing water and freshwater pools near a saline-alkaline lake . => (for Wetland Interior, FLK N) The edge of a perennial wetland abutting the topographically higher Peninsula to the south; proximity to open water (crocodyles, grebes, teals), wetlands (rails, small heron) and vegetation with sufficient cover, heavily wooded and perhaps even forested, with trees or bushes in the vicinity (dove, mousebird, lovebird). => (for Peninsula, FLK Patchily-treed narrow peninsula that rose approximately 0.5 to 1 m above the Wetland Complex to its north and the River Channel to its southeast, with trees along its southern face (high densities of micro-mammal remains) and open grassy habitat along part of the Peninsula facet (heavy competition for carcass-scavenging and high predation risk to hominids). Roosting trees or rocky outcrops in the vicinity (raptorial birds). A dry, low-light area where lichen is typically found. => (for Channel/Spillway, FLK S) A branching stream river flowed parallel to the Peninsula, likely seasonal, in the area of FLK S , with perennial sedges along river banks. The river have been of sufficient velocity to restrict or limit avian activity. It likely was an areas of heavy larger carnivore activity [K.A. Prassack, 2010, DOI: 10.3853/j.0067-1975.62.2010.1541]. The presence of crane, especially if it can be assigned to <i>Grus carunculatus</i> , would support the presence of open grasslands . Together with the ibis (<i>Geronticus eremita</i>), support a drier grassland/woodland signal more akin to Middle Bed I (Prassack, 2010) than lowermost Bed II (Prassack, 2014) [K.A. Prassack et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.003].	Fossils associated with OH 62 are of small to medium sized mammals and reptiles: <i>Kobus sigmodalis</i> , cf. Antelopini, cf. Alcelaphini, Giraffidae (cf. <i>Sivatherium</i>), Hippopotamidae, Suidae, Deinotheriidae, Carnivora (cf. large lutrine mustelid or viverrid), Cercopithecidae, Hystricidae, Cricetidae, Aves (cf. <i>Struthio</i>), Reptilia (Varanidae, <i>Crocodylus</i> , Serpentes, Chelonia), Amphibia (cf. <i>Anura</i>) and Pisces (<i>Clarias</i>) [D.C. Johanson et al., 1987, DOI: 10.1038/327205a0]. Felids, hyaenids (e.g., <i>Blumenschine, 1995</i>), and possibly other large mammal carnivores as well as crocodiles (Njau, 2006; Njau and Blumenschine, 2006) were also active at the FLK site [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. The <i>Zinjanthropus</i> land surface (FLK level 22) correlated to nearby FLK NN Level 1 , contained less abundant faunal remains (Leakey, 1971; Blumenschine et al., 2012b) [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006]. In between Sand to tuffaceous silt, Archaeological Level 2. Anthropogenic activity is marginal at AMK . Only one hominin-made mark and lithics and the recovery of some hominin remains provide evidence for hominin presence at AMK. Natural processes would have been responsible for the formation of AMK [J. Aramendi et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.02.036] (n.a. stratigraphic hier ?).	OH 5 "The Nutcracker Man" (calvaria with teeth), Paranthropus boisei , (<i>Zinjanthropus</i>), FLK I Level 22 , considered by the Leakeys to be "living floor" [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. OH 6 (cranial fragments), young hominid of about 4–7 years of age, FLK Level 22 , considered by the Leakeys to be "living floor" [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. OH 44 (one tooth), young hominid of about 4–7 years of age, FLK Level 22 , considered by the Leakeys to be "living floor" [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. OH 35 (tibia & fibula), Homo habilis , FLK Level 22 ; from deposits stratified between Tuff IB and Tuff IC, dating to between 1.845 and 1.839 Ma (Blumenschine et al., 2003). The proximal part of the leg was consumed by a leopard-like carnivore, while the distal part of it was damaged by a crocodile that likely disarticulated the foot. The consumer sequence is not clear [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. Great stratigraphic discrepancy, within a 6,000 year interval, between OH 8 and OH 35 [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. OH 62 ('Dik-dik hominid' parts of the skull–palate, face, calvaria, mandible and dentition, right humerus, radius a portion of the proximal ulna, femur, tibia), a very small body size Homo habilis (similar to A.L. 288-1 specimen of <i>Australopithecus afarensis</i>), discovered at Dik Dik Hill (DDH), capped in an colluvium, derived from lower Bed I sediments at FLK, near Geological Locality 45c, below Tuff ID, most probably from the sand lens between Tuff IC, roughly equivalent to the FLK – Zinjanthropus . The age of OH 62 is between the ages of Tuff IB and Tuff IF (ca. 1.8 Ma) [D.C. Johanson et al., 1987, DOI: 10.1038/327205a0].	Artefacts recovered on the surface at Dik Dik Hill (DDH) and in the lag deposit, are cores and flakes typical of the Oldowan industry . More than 95% of the lithic clasts in the colluvium (Trench 2) are positively correlated with deposits equivalent to and below Tuff ID [D.C. Johanson et al., 1987, DOI: 10.1038/327205a0]. The <i>Zinjanthropus</i> land surface (FLK level 22) correlated to nearby FLK NN Level 1 , contained scattered artifacts (Leakey, 1971; Blumenschine et al., 2012b) [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006].
			Fine black trachyandesitic ash tuff has been identified and sampled in trenches 144 and 147 slightly below Tuff IC at both FLK and FLK N ; suggests a distal fallout origin.		FLK, FLK N,						
			Chapati tuff (CHT) , an laminated reworked tuff present along the whole study area. It is composed by 3 main layer [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	Layer A – laminated thin layer, white to light yellow color , with green tuffaceous clay	Lake-parasequences 2 (1.853.400 – 1.849.200 Ma) , FLK, FLK-N, FLK-NN, Maiko Gully N (n.a. after Fig. 5 [J.G. Stanistreet,	PKT (Level 3), FLK Complex,	Two fish taxa were identified: <i>Clarias</i> sp. (catfish) and Cichlidae (tilapia). The fish remains are interpret to be the result of natural deposition in shallow, freshwater [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2010, DOI:	The third level at PTK , underlying the Zinj clay , yielded a large faunal assemblage [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms8987].	OH 86 (manual proximal phalanx), modern human like (MH1), PTK (Philip Tobias Korongo) site, [M. Dominguez-Rodrigo et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms8987].	Chapati tuff (CHT) is the sedimentary context where the PTK archaeological level is documented [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023]. The third level at PTK , underlying	

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2015.10.005], [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact	
			Chapati tuff contains level FLK NN2 [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001.)			10.1016/j.yqres.2010.07.003].			the Zinj clay, yielded abundant Mode I stone artefacts [M. Domínguez-Rodrigo et al., 2015, DOI: 10.1038/ncomms8987].	
			Layer B – massive thicker layer gray colored, with tephra fragments, matrix-supported vitric tuff.		PKT, FLK Complex,						
			Layer C – massive thin tuff layer, white, with very thin laminates of carbonate,		PKT, FLK, FLK-NN, FLK Complex,						
			Tuffaceous Clay, green olive color, compact and massive, with root marks [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	Stage 4 in the evolution of the Zinj paleolandscape: archaeological deposit of FLK-NN3 surface, FLK-NN2 and PTK-3 levels were formed [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	Lake-parasequences 3 (1.845 – 1.853.400 Ma), FLK, FLK-N, FLK-NN, Maiko Gully (n.a. after Fig. 5 [J.G. Stanistreet, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.001].)			The OH 7/OH 8 land surface, at a lower level (level 3) within the same FLK NN excavation, produced a large assemblage of vertebrate fossils [Leakey, 1971] [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006].	Chapati tuff overlies the archaeological level FLKNN 3 (OH7 and OH8). At FLK-NN3, the top of the Tuffaceous Clay is the surface of OH-7 and OH-8 [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023]. OH 7, “Johnny’s Child” (hand, lower jaw, cranial fragments), type specimen of <i>Homo habilis</i> , roughly 1.8 Ma, at the FLK North-North site, Level 3, considered by the Leakeys to be “living floor”. (OH 7 matches the type specimen of <i>Homo habilis</i> [R.J. Clarke, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.11.007].) OH 8 (articulated set of tarsal and metatarsal bones), paratype of <i>Homo habilis</i> , FLK NN site [Hay, 1976: Locality 45b], Level 3, considered by the Leakeys to be “living floor”; from deposits stratified between Tuff IB and Tuff IC, dating to between 1.845 and 1.839 Ma [Blumenschine et al., 2003]. Tooth marks on the specimen’s ankle reveal the hominid had been a crocodile’s lunch [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008]. OH 48 (adult clavicle), FLK NN Level 3, considered by the Leakeys to be “living floor” [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008] (n.a.: stratigraphic hier ?). OH 49 (radius shaft), FLK NN Level 3, considered by the Leakeys to be “living floor” [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008] (n.a.: stratigraphic hier ?). OH 50 (rib), FLK NN Level 3, considered by the Leakeys to be “living floor” [Leakey, 1959, 1960; Leakey, 1971] [J.K. Njau, R.J. Blumenschine, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.008] (n.a.: stratigraphic hier ?).	Tuffaceous Clay is the archaeological level of FLK-NN3 [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].	
			Clay Tuff, pale yellow and light olive grey colors, bioturbated with carbonated roots [D. Uribelarrea et al., 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2013.12.023].		PKT, FLK Complex,						
			Mt. Olmoti volcanism had not yet initiated [McHenry, 2012] [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011]				After Tuff IB deposition, Olmoti eruptions caused a westward displacement of the lake to the position it held throughout the remainder of Bed I time [F.T. Masao, S. Anton & J.K. Njau, 2013, DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.2004.2964, ISBN: 978-9961-716-55-7].				
		1.848 ± 0.003 Ma (overall weighted-mean, in the middle) (1.845 ± 0.002 Ma [R. J. Blumenschine et al., 2003, DOI: 10.1126/science.107534])	Tuff IB, at Loc. 13 the base is 1.851 ± 0.005 Ma (13-1af) and the lignimite 1.852 ± 0.008 Ma (13-middle) 1ig). field relationships suggest that the Plinian base was erupted just prior to deposition of the lignimite. In the FLK area Tuff IB is largely reworked, suggesting deposition over a relatively long time period.	(FLK [Hay, 1976: Loc 45]) Succession of pumice-rich pyroclastic flow and minor surge deposits, 7.6-m-thick, with the top surface, rooted and/or deformed in many places by animal trampling.	(FLK [Hay, 1976: Loc 45]) Another yellowish fallout ash (8–24 cm) unit or coarse, wave-reworked volcaniclastic sandstones (~60 cm), characterized by admixed lacustrine clays, small soft clay clasts, and ostracod and snail shells.	Deposition of Tuff IB was immediately followed by lake expansion resulting in the deposition of green waxy claystone. It is coincident within 2σ error with the highest amplitude peak of the entire insolation time series of the Bed I/Lower Bed II interval at 1.852 Ma [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].					
				(FLK [Hay, 1976: Loc 45]) Feldspar-rich fallout tuff (McHenry, 2005), (1–5 cm), most primary		The Olmoti Fan-delta originated with the Olmoti eruption that produced Tuff IB [Stanistreet et al., this volume] [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267]. Evidence of freshwater and preserved marshland vegetation buried by Tuff IB at KK W just east of FLK [Bamford, 2012] [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267].					

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.10.005], [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact
						around 1.864 - around 1.868.200 Ma At the transition from D1 to W1 a pronounced shift in the aquatic organisms of Paleolake Olduvai, suggesting that some ecological threshold was crossed. The terrestrial vegetation exhibit a more gradual trend across the dry-wet boundary associated with the transition from open grassland to more wooded vegetation (after Fig. 3 [D.E. Calcord et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.04.001]).				
		1.877.000 - 1.871.200 Ma (1.848 ± 0.003 Ma plus 5800 x 5 yr)	Lake-parasequences P1, is dominated by nearshore lacustrine sandy claystone (Trenches 2 and 3) and diamictic mass flow facies (Trench 9) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.11.011].		DK,	DK, Lake-parasequences P1, an extreme and abrupt shallowing of the lake and temporary establishment of a dry lake flat in its deepest area (claystone and even sandy claystone facies) (OGCP core 2A, 2°58'43"S, 35°19'25.5"E, 2014) [D.E. Calcord et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2018.01.023]. Palaeolake Olduvai dry event D1 - around 1.868.200 - 1.872 Ma (after Fig. 3 [D.E. Calcord et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.04.001]).			- In Trenches 3, 5 and 10 (DK), a pale surface with relief suggestive of a foot printed surface was encountered at the base of Level 4 [F.T. Masao et al., 2009, Symposium, ISBN: 978-9961-716-55-7] (n.a. is Level 4 hier ?).	
			Mafic Tuff III (east) [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026].	The 3 basalt flows represented as basaltic scoria-bearing layers (core 3A) were emplaced during a single precessional cycle (~23 kyr), within the timespan of two parasequences only, suggesting as little as 6 kyr to as much as 15 kyr [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].		Basalt Mbr. After the Bed I Basalt, and until the deposition of Tuff IB, is a period of apparent volcanic quiet [A.M. Shilling et al., 2019, PII: S0031-0182(19)30138-5, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109267].				
			Volcaniclastic & siliciclastic (?) (from: Fig. 9 [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026]). Basaltic scoria-bearing layers (Borehole 3A) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].							
			Mafic Tuff II, (west) [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026].							
			Basaltic scoria-bearing layers (Borehole 3A) [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].							
		1.877 ± 0.013 Ma 1.956 ± 0.031 Ma (n.a. NEW from Fig. 2 in [Stanistreet et al., 2020])	Bed I Lavas (Basalt), Upper Bed I and Lower Bed I separated by the Bed I basaltic lavas in the East.							
		1.893 Ma	minima in eccentricity [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].	Lower Bed I Mbr.						
		1.918 Ma (interpolated age)	Tuff IA, geochemical type locality 65. Tuff IA formed from fluvial reworking of a fallout ash into shallow lacustrine successions, subsequently pedogenically modified [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].	(increased moisture), peaking at about 2.027, 1.939 (wet period W6), and 1.845 Ma, respectively, and two minima in eccentricity, peaking at about 1.989 and 1.893 Ma, respectively (Deino, 2012) [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)]. The shadow effect of the Ngorongoro Volcanic Highlands during the deposition of the Ngorongoro Formation (~2.2 Ma to 2.0 Ma), after which Olmoti Volcano developed during deposition of Bed I (~1.85 to 1.80 Ma). Loolmalasin and Empagai (during deposition of Beds II, III, and IV) and even younger volcanoes, completed the climatic barrier [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109656].		Major freshening event in the paleo-Lake Olduvai basin occurred ca. 1.89 Ma (event 2) [D.M. Deocampo et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1130/G38950.1].				
		1.939 Ma	maxima in eccentricity [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].		Loc 66e (between Granite Falls and 6th Fault, western Olduvai Gorge),	Evidence for the presence of Paleolake Olduvai in the exposed Olduvai sequence between Naabi Ignimbrite and Tuff IA. Coincides with the intensification of the Walker circulation [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)]. (Loc 66e) The immature woodland community cluster without palms, grew adjacent to a widely spaced network of small, shallow braided stream channels that incised the pedogenically encrusted top of a volcaniclastic mass-flow deposit at Loc 66e. Another low-viscosity mass flow then buried the bottom part of the trees in their upright living position. There is no evidence from the presence of saline-alkaline Paleolake Olduvai at the time the trees were growing, but clues for the proximity of freshwater (shallow streams or springs) [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011].				Some quartzite Oldowan lithic artefacts Loc 66e, are associated with the woody landscape. The artifactual quartzitic material was most probably brought in by hominin agency and possibly derived from basement exposures north of the gorge [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011].
			Base of Olduvai Subchron, 1.945 ± 4 ka.							
		1.989 Ma	minima in eccentricity [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].							
		~2 Ma	Initiation of an episode of minor faulting in the Tanzanian sector, ~2 Ma [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].							

Formation	Sediment Accretion Rate	Age [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004].	Strata definition, Sequences & Layers [L.J. McHenry, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010], [L.J. McHenry, H. Stollhofen, I.G. Stanistreet, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2013.05.006], [L.J. McHenry et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.yqres.2015.10.005], [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.01.005], [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].	Stratigraphy	Site, Loc.	Palaeolandscape & Palaeoclimate	Ecosystem Aves	Ecosystem Mammalia	Homo & Homo-like	Artefact
Ngorongoro Volcanic Formation		2.015 ± 0.006 Ma (overall mean, at the base)	Coarse-Feldspar Crystal Tuff (CFCT) , geochemical type locality 61. Pale-red, feldspar-phyric ash-lapilli tuff (Orkeri outcrop [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026]). The CFCT zone is compositionally zoned, with ilmenite more abundant at its top and titanomagnetite near its base, and the ignimbrite exposure at Loc 9a corresponds to the top unit [L.J. McHenry et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109630].							
		2.003 ± 0.006 Ma (n.a. NEW from Fig. 2 in [Stanistreet et al., 2020])								
			Mafic Tuff , geochemical type locality 64 (this Mafic Tuff ?). (Mafic Tuff I [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026])							
		2.005 ± 0.007 Ma (n = 5 of 8) (weighted-mean) (n.a.: The author put the Lowermost tuff in Bed I over the Naabi Ignimbrite and under Mafic Tuff)	Lowermost tuff in Bed I (sample 81x-p), 0.5m beneath the CFCT marker unit							
		2.027 Ma	maxima in eccentricity [J.M. Habermann, 2016 (Thesis)].							
		2.038 ± 0.005 Ma , sample 67-2p 2.033 ± 0.001 Ma (n.a. NEW from Fig. 2 in [Stanistreet et al., 2020])	Naabi Ignimbrite , geochemical type locality 64. Gray-green, quartz- and anorthoclase-phyric, welded lapilli-ash tuff (Orkeri outcrop). The green ignimbrite exposed along the 1st Fault (Orkeri outcrop, described in Habermann et al., 2016). Lower Bed I tuffs linked to Ngorongoro and suggests that uplift along the 1st Fault may be more significant than was previously thought.							
	2.047 ± 0.003 Ma (n.a. NEW from Fig. 2 in [Stanistreet et al., 2020])	Orkeri Ignimbrite , brown-beige, lithic- and pumice-rich ash-lapilli tuff at the 1st Fault [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026]. Pre-Orkeri, Hornblende rich Pre-Orkeri, mafic glass Pre-Orkeri, high-Fe augite								
Naibor Sait Formation 2.12 – 2.09 Ma		2.0803 ± 0.0041 Ma	No name, (n.a. NEW from Fig. ? in [Stanistreet et al., 2020]).							
		2.167 ± 0.002 Ma	No name, (n.a. NEW from Fig. ? in "New Olduvai Basin stratigraphy and stratigraphic concepts revealed by OGCP cores into the Palaeolake Olduvai depocentre, Tanzania" [J.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751], hereafter Stanistreet et al., 2020).							
	Sedimentation began at this (n.a.: core) site in the Olduvai Basin at ~2.5 Ma [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990].									

- Acronyms for Olduvai Gorge sites:

- Loc 66e** (Locality 66e), between Granite Falls and 6th Fault, western Olduvai Gorge.
- AMK** (Amin Mturi Korongo), situated in the Secondary Gorge, at the eastern Olduvai paleolake alluvial plain (~500 m from FLK-Zinj and 200 m away from PTK).
- BK** (Bell's Korongo, Localitie 64 ?) site is situated on the south wall of the Side Gorge, 3 km upstream from its junction with the Main Gorge. It consists of two krongos linked by a short cliff.
- Dal.K** (Dalmatian Korongo) is the next gully on the left bank on the main gorge upstream of PLK.
- DDH** (Dik Dik Hill), **EF-HR** (Evelyn Fuchs-Hans Reck),
- DK** (Douglas Korongo, Archaeological site number 22 and Geological locality 13), ~2.5 km east of the 'junction area' where the Main Gorge and Side Gorge join, on the lower slopes of an alluvial fan, at a **broad shallow playa** that occupied the centre of the basin near the outer edge of palaeo Lake Olduvai on the north side of the Olduvai River, Olduvai Basin. Trenches **DKI**, **DKIA**, and **DKIB** (the **main Leakey DK**).
- DS** (David's Site), Bed I,
- FC** (Fuch's Cliff) site located in the North side of the Olduvai Gorge, around 1.3 km west from the 3rd Fault. **FC W** (Fuch's Cliff West).
- **FC West** site lies lower than the nearby **FC** (Fuch's Cliff) site, and is located in the Side Gorge, around 1.6 km from the junction with the Main Gorge. FC West is stratigraphically situated in the Middle Member of Bed II [from: <http://www.olduvai-gorge.org/index.html>, on 01.05.2020, at 10:06 AM].
- FLK** (Frida Leakey Korongo) main **complex** (FLK-NN, FLK-N, PTK, FLK-Zinj), **FLK Zinj** (Leakey's (1971) classic *Zinjanthropus* Site Locality 45), level **22** (**FLK 22 Zinj**). The **FLK Zinj** site occupies the southernmost gully of the area comprised by the FLK sites (FLK, FLK N and FLK NN) (Leakey, 1971), enclosed in the (green) waxy clay sediments overlain by Tuff **IC**. **FLK N**, described as **Loc 45a** by Richard Hay (Hay, 1976) is situated in uppermost Bed I, <100 m north of the FLK 22 *Zinjanthropus* (FLK Zinj) site. **FLK NN** (Frida Leakey Korongo North-North), **FLK-W** / **FLKW** (FLK West). **FLK Maiko** (or **Maiko Gully**, between FLK and FLS, southeast from FLK-W). **FLK S**, **GTC** (... Loc. 95), a low cliff on the left bank of the side gorge, immediately upstream of MRC.
- HEB** (Heberer's Gully) site, (2°59' 44.4"S, 35°21' 0.5"E), situated on a relatively steep 40° northfacing slope on the edge of the gorge, approximately two hundred meters north of the Olduvai Gorge Museum [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773]. A small gully on the south face of HWK.
- HK** (Hopwood's Korongo),
- HWK** (Loc. 42), **HWK E** (Henrietta Wilfrida Korongo East), **HWK Head of Gully** (46c), **HWK EE** (HWK East East), **HWK EE-Tembo**. **HWK W** lies to the southeast of the confluence of the Main and Side Gorges, to the southeast of the main access road to FLK Zinj (Frida Leakey Korongo, Zinjanthropus site) and the Leakey Camp.
- **HWKEE** is stratigraphically located between Tuffs (volcanic ash) **IIA** and **IIB** in Bed II [from: <http://www.olduvai-gorge.org/index.html>, on 01.05.2020, at 10:06 AM].
- JK** (Juma Korongo, geological Localitie 14), renamed JK2 because of Louis Leakey's uncertainty over the original location of the site he had named "JK" (Kleindienst, pers. comm.). Is located on the north side of the Gorge, 2.2 km east of where the main and side gorges meet [M.C. Pante, 2013, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102885>].
- KK** (Kudu Korongo), a gully on the right bank of the gorge, immediately downstream of HWK East.
- LK** (Leakey's Korongo) lies on the left bank of the Gorge and is the first gully upstream of the 3rd fault.
- Long K** (Long Korongo, geological Localitie 10), **LLK** (),

MCK (Margaret Cropper Korongo),

MK (Macinnes Korongo, geologic **Localitie 11**), situated on the left bank of the Gorge, half a mile downstream from DK. **MK W (MK West, geological Localitie ?)**,

MNK (Mary Nicol Korongo, **Locality 88**) lies on the Side Gorge, opposite from FC (Fuch's Cliff) site, about 1.3 km from the confluence of the Main and Side Gorges. Includes two localities, the Skull Site and the Main Occupation Site.

PTK (Philip Tobias Korongo) site, ~500 m south of the well-known FLK 22 Zinjanthropus (FLK 22 Zinj) site.

RHC (Richard Hay Cliff = **Loc. 80 of Hay (1976)**), an almost vertical cliff on the left bank of the gorge, c. ¼ mi from the 5th fault, facing south-east.

RK (Reck's Korongo, geologic **Localitie 9**),

SHK (Sam Howard Korongo, locality **91**) site is located in the mouth of a lateral gully that debouches in the right bank, of the Side Gorge approximately 1 km from BK (Bell Korongo), about 2 km from the confluence with the Main Gorge, and comprise two areas: the Main (**SHKM**) site (a fluvial channel and its over-bank) and the Annexe (**SHKA**), an alluvial plain situated nearby the channel, about 90 m further up the Main site. **SHKE** (SHK Extension)

TK (Thiongo Korongo) site located on the Upper Bed II, to the north slope of the Main Gorge, some 2 km east of the joining point with the Side Gorge. An age of c. 1.3 My has been estimated. **TKSF** (Sivatherium Floor at the site of TK), **TKLF** (TK Lower Floor), **TKUF** (TK Upper Floor),

VCS (Victoria Cabrera Site),

VEK (Vivian Evelin Korongo, geologic **Localitie 86**),

WK (Wayland's Korongo),

Trench (**T**)

valleys (korongos = K, e.g. FLK), **cliffs** (= C, e.g. RHC)

Olduvai Hominin (**OH**)

modern human-like (**MHL**)

Crocodile Valley Incision Surface (**CVIS**)

HWK EE **LC** (Leakey Clay), HWK EE **LSC** (Leakey Sandy Conglomerate)

Brown Tuffaceous Siltstone (**BTS**)

Lower Augitic Sandstone (**LAS**)

Middle Augitic Sandstone (**MAS**)

Ngorongoro Volcanic Highlands (**NVH**)

Chapati tuff (**CHT**)

- **OGCP** (Olduvai Gorge Coring Project) Cores **1A** (2°59'8.2"S, 35°20'34.1"E), **2A** (2°58'43.0"S, 35°19'25.5"E), and **3A/3B** (2°56'41.6"S, 35°22'51.5"E) [*L.J. McHenry et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109630*].